

Prevailing Moral Standards in Higher Education Institutions

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the moral standards within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) among faculty and students, employing a phenomenological approach. Through qualitative methodology, it examined the lived experiences of six faculty and six students from diverse HEIs via in-depth interviews. The findings revealed structured standards aligned with the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers, emphasizing values such as respect, honesty, integrity, and social responsibility. Additionally, unwritten moral standards reflect participants' lived experiences, covering spirituality, empathy, accountability, fairness, and personal well-being. In addition, it identified three interconnected factors influencing ethical behavior: moral character, interaction, and environment. Traits like integrity and self-discipline form the foundation for ethical conduct. Positive interactions, such as empathy and compassion, foster a supportive atmosphere. The moral environment, marked by responsibility and justice, shapes societal and institutional contexts for ethical behavior. By nurturing moral character, encouraging positive interactions, and fostering ethical environments, HEIs can promote ethical behavior and improve educational quality. This research enhanced understanding of moral standards in HEIs, offering insights to enhance educational experiences and promote a morally upright society within institutions.

Keywords: Ethics, Morality, Values, Ethical Principles, Higher Education

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Introduction

Higher education institutions have traditionally aimed to foster intellectual growth and moral development. However, the focus on academic achievement and the development of competencies often eclipses the cultivation of ethical values. While universities have established codes of conduct to promote integrity, fairness, and respect, a gap exists between these formal guidelines and the personal moral frameworks faculty and students bring to and develop within academic settings. Bročić and Miles (2021) mentioned that college education generally liberalizes students' moral views, particularly in areas of social justice and compassion. They challenge stereotypes about college as a purely liberalizing force. Surprisingly, it also strengthens belief in universal moral principles rather than promoting moral relativism. This influence is most pronounced among humanities, arts, and social sciences students and is even stronger for graduate students.

Educational institutions believe students will bring this to their future endeavors by teaching them proper morals, conduct, and other ethical principles. The study of Andersson et al. (2022) shows that ethics education helps professionals and students better understand and handle ethical issues. They emphasized the need for support to manage these issues effectively, increase awareness of ethical problems, and improve decision-making skills. Additionally, it identifies various course designs and content that can help prepare healthcare workers and students for ethical challenges in their practice.

In the Philippines, seeing the challenges experienced by the students and the desire to achieve their goals, such as obtaining a degree, completing academic requirements, and avoiding disappointments from their family or friends, there comes a time when they need to achieve them by hook or by crook. Caslib (2022) stated that the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on ethics education in the Philippines brought significant challenges to the students and teachers, such as poor internet connectivity and difficulties in aligning online teaching methods with learning outcomes. The effectiveness of online ethics

education due to the country's limited internet infrastructure has been questioned because of the students' capacity and availability to attend classes and cope with the requirements. Hence, there is a chance that students may use unethical ways to comply with their requirements, and, worse, to pass their quizzes and examinations online.

Thus, this research aims to understand moral education's importance and advocate for its integration with academic pursuits. Studies have shown that explicit ethical guidelines embedded in the curriculum can encourage ethical behavior in students and faculty. However, the practical application and interpretation of these guidelines vary, leading to inconsistencies in moral expectations across institutions. This study sought to identify and analyze prevailing moral standards within higher education institutions, drawing from the firsthand experiences of faculty and students. Specifically, it aimed to know the structured ethical standards outlined in institutional codes of ethics for faculty and students, their personal, unstructured moral standards based on their educational experiences, and how the ideal moral standards might contribute to enhancing the quality of higher education. Seeing the gaps in the field of the study may contribute more not only to the institutions involved in this research but also to all institutions facing the same problem. This will then lead to identifying the gaps and bringing forth necessary actions and solutions for the betterment and integrity of education and for the moral development of the students.

Ethics Education

In ethics, five fundamental theories guide moral deliberation. Virtue ethics focuses on character and practical wisdom (Silverman & Buckland, 2020); rights-based ethics emphasizes safeguarding universal rights (Kapoor, 2019); deontology centers on moral obligations (Barrow & Khandhar, 2023); utilitarianism aims to maximize happiness (Mitra, 2019); and the ethics of care highlights empathy and relationality (Ley, 2023). Understanding these theories fosters good character, healthy relationships, and ethical leadership in higher education institutions (HEIs). Scholars advocate for integrating moral education into HEIs, emphasizing ethical leadership and

virtues. This holistic approach includes all facets of university life, from policies to faculty conduct (Tesar et al., 2021; Buzzelli & Johnston, 2002).

Implementing moral education faces challenges. These challenges include the unintended negative consequences of school policies (Thornberg, 2009), situational ethics (Fletcher, 1966), and advocating for universal principles while acknowledging complexities (Lillegard, 2020). On a positive note, moral education leads the students to a better way of life. Some international organizations emphasize values like respect and critical thinking as the fruits of moral or ethical education (OECD, 2019). Scholars also link success with moral values (Ambrose, 2009) and highlight ethical leadership's role in promoting positive behavior and educational excellence (Amir et al., 2023). Leaders must integrate moral education into practices, fostering character development and ethical decision-making (Riaz & Normore, 2008).

The Ethics of Community emphasizes collaboration and shared responsibility (Furman, 2004; Greene, 2019). Ethical leadership is crucial for recognizing moral issues and aligning with institutional goals (Englehart, 2010). Scholars advocate for values education in HEIs to promote personal growth and social well-being (Muega, 2010; Bautista, 2018). Research on psychosocial factors affecting student well-being offers insights for interventions (Morales-Rodriguez et al., 2020; Muassomah et al., 2022). Promoting ethical behavior in education emphasizes moral standards and character development (Ramberg & Modin, 2019).

Studies by Muega (2010) and Bautista (2018) emphasize strengthening values education against influences like religion, family, and media. Catacutan and de Guzman (2015) show how ethical frameworks guide administrators' decisions. Alvarez (2020) and Gabatbat and Santander (2021) advocate for ethical instruction to address contemporary challenges and promote well-being. Toker Gökçe (2021) highlights preservice teachers' role in fostering ethical, diverse classrooms.

Baird and McCaig (2022) advocate integrating ethics education throughout all university courses rather than isolating it in specific

classes. They propose a three-stage model: first, introducing students to ethical dilemmas; second, teaching them how to address these dilemmas; and third, supporting their development towards ethical maturity. This approach aims to prepare graduates who can balance personal and community values and handle complex ethical issues effectively. With their advocacy, bringing into light the important effects of morality and ethics in education will ensure the development of the students.

Piragauta and de Oliveira's (2022) mentioned that the role of ethics and values in online education led both students and teachers to consider responsibility, commitment, and respect crucial in virtual learning. They also reveal that students and teachers have somewhat different online ethical experiences. Hence, they suggest that online teaching methods should be re-evaluated to place greater emphasis on ethics. With this, ethics education can be instilled all the more, not only at the academic level but also in the impression of ethics in the students' lives.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative design to explore moral standards among administrators, faculty, and students in higher education using the phenomenological method. This approach focuses on understanding subjective experiences (Moran, 2000), allowing the phenomenon to guide the method (Hycner, 1999), and emphasizing honest description without predefined structures (Giorgi, 2009).

Participants were purposively selected to capture diverse experiences, including faculty with over ten years of experience and 3rd and 4th-year students from various academic backgrounds. The study included 12 participants: six professors (aged 36 to 57) and six students (aged 20 to 23) from private non-sectarian, private Catholic, and public non-sectarian universities, ensuring a comprehensive exploration of moral standards.

Primary data were collected through one-on-one interviews with open-ended questions. Twelve respondents were selected from three higher educational institutions: private, public, and

non-sectarian. Each institution provided two senior faculty members and two senior or penultimate-year students. Interviews were conducted privately, following Husserl's bracketing method to suspend judgments and preconceptions.

Findings

Structured & Written Ethical Standards

Table 1 shows the comparison of the written moral standards of the respective universities, which share a common ground, which is evident in

Table 1. Comparison of Written Moral Standards

Moral Values	University X	University Y	University Z	Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers
Respect	Uphold respect for others and academic integrity	Respect the university's identity, create a respectful environment	Respect the rights and dignity of all community members	Respect students' dignity, rights, and freedom, avoid discrimination or harassment
Honesty and Integrity	Practice honesty, fairness, and avoid academic dishonesty	Behave honestly and with integrity in all interactions	Uphold honesty and integrity in all interactions	Maintain professional integrity, honesty, and avoid plagiarism or dishonesty
Cooperation	Collaborate and maintain professionalism	Join organizations aligned with the university's vision	Foster cooperation and maintain campus cleanliness	Collaborate with colleagues, promote respect and cooperation among students
Social Responsibility	Contribute to society through actions and decisions	Engage in community betterment	Consider the impact of actions on others	Promote student welfare, provide a safe environment, and contribute to Society
Professionalism	Conduct oneself professionally and report ethical violations	Develop professionalism among faculty and employees	Demonstrate professionalism in character and academics	Uphold professionalism, avoid conflicts of interest, and maintain confidentiality
Accountability	Take responsibility for actions and behavior	Be accountable for actions and their consequences	Be accountable for behavior and its consequences	Take responsibility for actions, be accountable, and report potential abuse or neglect
Continuous Professional Growth	Strive for academic excellence and engage in professional development	Foster lifelong learning opportunities and ongoing professional development	Pursue academic excellence and ongoing professional development	Engage in continuous professional growth, keep up-to-date, and seek professional development
Compliance with laws and Regulations	Abide by university's conduct rules and regulations	Comply with laws and regulations	Comply with laws and regulations	Comply with teaching profession's laws, regulations, and standards

the emphasis on respecting the rights, dignity, and freedom from harassment of everyone within their communities. Upholding honesty and integrity in academic work and interactions is another crucial principle. Finally, taking responsibility for actions and behavior is a key tenet for both faculty and students.

The universities' values align significantly with the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers. This focus on student well-being translates into all institutions prioritizing a safe, inclusive environment that avoids discrimination.

While core values provide a strong foundation, each university offers additional considerations. University X emphasizes academic freedom and intellectual honesty. In contrast, University Y prioritized social responsibility and fostering a culture of transparency. University Z brings a unique perspective by integrating religious

values with respect for humanity and democracy.

Moral Values and Identity

In Table 2, University X, moral goodness centers on genuine concern for others, exemplified by selflessness and perseverance amid exhaustion. Yet, confronting past mistakes poses a challenge to self-acceptance. At University Y, avoiding harm and fostering personal growth are priorities, emphasizing responsible language and accountability. Despite grappling with guilt, students prioritized open communication. At University Z, respecting boundaries while meeting standards is paramount. Here, students prioritized self-acceptance for personal growth, defining goodness as aiding others and embracing mistakes. Each university offered unique perspectives on moral values and identity, shaping students' understanding of goodness and their place in the world.

Table 2. Moral Values and Identity

Feature	University X	University Y	University Z
Professors' Values	Genuine concern, empathy, addressing misconduct	Power of language, accountability, individual well-being	Ethical standards, self-reflection, forgiveness
Students' Values	Altruism, selflessness, coping with guilt and isolation, addressing misconduct	Dealing with mistakes contextually, prioritizing forgiveness, fostering healthy relationships	Personal accountability, self-compassion, navigating guilt and forgiveness, handling misconduct thoughtfully
Learning from mistakes	Emphasis on growth mindset	Emphasis on individual reflection and learning	Emphasis on personal growth and offering multiple chances
Guilt and Forgiveness	Students grapple with guilt and seek forgiveness	Students experience intense guilt and seek support	Students manage guilt through self-reflection and forgiveness
Relationship Focus	Prioritizing others' needs	Prioritizing personal well-being	Prioritizing healthy relationships and fostering trust
Handling Misconduct	Addressing directly and empathetically	Emphasizing communication and minimizing harm	Employing direct confrontation and guidance for friends

Moral Attributes

At University X, Professors C and D stressed celebrating colleagues' achievements and fighting for justice alongside humility and

respect for fellow teachers. Student D urged peers to persevere towards future goals. University Y's Professors A and B advocated charity, purity, and giving the benefit of the doubt, warning against revenge and false information. Student A values a

respectful classroom atmosphere. At University Z, Professors F and E and Students E and F emphasized understanding, humility, respect, and honesty as defining traits of goodness. Overall, each institution emphasized different facets of moral values and personal character in shaping students' perspectives (see Table 3).

Dreams and Priorities: Personal Values and Aspirations

At University X, Professors C and D emphasized simplicity and seeking diverse accomplishments. Student C aspires to make a social impact as a diplomat representing refugees, while Student D prioritizes health, studies, and family. At University Y, Professors A and B valued peace of mind, satisfaction, and contentment surrounded by loved ones, echoed by students' desires for material wealth and financial stability. At University Z, Professors E and F prioritized having a good source of necessities and seeing their families healthy, while students prioritized family, friends, and

self-care, highlighting the importance of familial relationships and personal well-being (see Table 3)

Institutional Policies and Moral Environment

At University X, Professors prioritized loyalty over qualifications and lamented excessive accreditation requirements, questioning academic freedom. Prof. D emphasized teaching citizenship responsibilities. Students felt policies lacked character-building aspects but appreciated them for order and future readiness. At University Y, Professors noted fair policies with room for flexibility, although concerns like internet expenses persist. Students appreciate prompt responses but remain uncertain about issue resolution and cite organizational and facility shortcomings. At University Z, professors found policies supportive but noted deficiencies in facilities and the need for skills updates. Budget cuts hinder resource requests, and some policies are perceived as favoring administration over fairness, as students find merit policies overly strict (see Table 3).

Table 3. Institutional Policies and Moral Environment

Aspect	University X	University Y	University Z
Moral Standards	Fairness, Academic Freedom, Order, Moral Character, Discipline, Moral Principles	Fairness, Flexibility, Well-being, Respect, Transparency, Consistency	Service and Support, Academic Freedom, Fairness, Inclusivity, Adaptability, Consideration
Areas for Improvement	Administrative transparency, fostering supportive environment, balance between policy enforcement & personal development	Faculty internet expenses, fostering a friendlier environment, fair class sizes, ensuring adequate resources, enhancing transparency in issue resolution	Faculty retraining support, budget constraints, improving facility availability
Specific Concerns	Patron-client relationships, excessive emphasis on accreditations, civic engagement	Transparency, fairness, consistency, support policies	Faculty retraining support, budget constraints, facility availability

Moral Challenges and Decision-Making

At University X, Professors C and D upheld integrity, refusing bribes and resisting unethical practices, even at the cost of their careers. Students confront discrimination and challenge authority when faced with unacceptable views or orders.

At University Y, faculty like Professors A and B exemplified ethical values, with some students succumbing to cheating under academic pressure while others uphold honesty. These experiences underscored the necessity of support systems to nurture ethical decision-making. At University Z, professors and students prioritized ethical

Table 4. Moral Challenges and Decision-Making

Feature	University X	University Y	University Z
Emphasis on Integrity	Strong commitment to integrity	Values integrity but exposes challenges	Deep-seated commitment to integrity
Response to Ethical Quandaries	Uphold ethical values with courage and critical thinking	Mixed responses, some succumb to pressures, others refuse to compromise	Individuals weigh opportunities against moral rectitude
Approach to Academic Pressure	Critical thinking and open dialogue	Acknowledges conflict between pressures and commitments, emphasizes support mechanisms	Struggles to balance opportunities and ethical integrity amidst pervasive pressure
Overall Approach	Fosters resilience and promotes ethical decision-making	Addresses underlying factors that can lead to ethical lapses	Focuses on ethical decision-making processes and developing coping mechanisms

behavior, refusing involvement in wrongdoing and considering the impact on others. They emphasized weighing moral considerations in decision-making processes (see Table 4).

Ideal Moral Standard to Improve the Quality of Higher Education

Research has found essential ethical standards from the perspectives of faculty and students in higher education institutions (HEIs). Analyzing 47 moral values from their experiences, key dimensions identified include spirituality, dignity, moral integrity, altruism, empathy, responsibility, forgiveness, sincerity, humility, contentment, simplicity, happiness, love of family, health, welfare, principles, relationships, perseverance, service, unity, critical thinking, independence, inclusivity, diligence, courtesy, passion, time management, social involvement, resilience, academic freedom, fairness, self-discipline, and respect for authority. These values represent crucial ethical principles that should be promoted within higher education.

Significant ideal moral standards that can enhance higher education quality are identified. They fall into three categories of moral synergy: moral character, moral interaction, and moral

environment. The moral character category included values such as spirituality, integrity, honesty, humility, forgiveness, resilience, happiness, love of family, well-being, commitment, positivity, success, and self-discipline. The moral interaction category covered selfless help, caring for others, empathy, compassion, and friendliness. Lastly, the moral environment category comprises responsibility, accountability, respect for rights and freedom, fairness, justice, service, and unity. These values are essential for fostering an ethical and enriching educational experience.

Discussion

This study addressed a critical gap in the existing literature by investigating prevailing moral standards in higher education institutions (HEIs) through a phenomenological research approach based on five Reflective Experiences (REs). Understanding and promoting moral standards in HEIs are essential for character development and ethical decision-making. The study provides rich insights into participants’ experiences of moral character, moral interaction, and the moral environment within HEIs. The findings regarding moral character, moral interaction, and the moral environment contribute to our understanding of

the factors that shape ethical behavior and promote a positive and ethical society. While these concepts have been studied in fields such as psychology, philosophy, and sociology, the novel contribution lies in their comprehensive analysis and the recognition of their interconnectedness.

The moral character embodies the qualities and virtues that make an individual morally upright and responsible. However, moral character alone is insufficient, as goodness is relational. A person is considered good in relation to others, and our good qualities must benefit others. The moral character gains true significance when translated into actions that positively impact those around us.

Recognizing that goodness flourishes in relation to others, moral interaction stresses the significance of constructive and compassionate connections with fellow human beings. Through good and loving relationships, people grow and learn how to live genuinely as human beings. Harmonious and empathetic interactions uplift and

inspire each other, resulting in the collective growth of ethical values and mutual support.

The moral environment plays a crucial role in sustaining and enhancing individuals' foundational qualities. Just as an unhealthy environment can weaken one's good qualities, a nurturing and supportive environment can bolster and amplify them. By cultivating a moral environment that upholds ethical values, fosters empathy, and encourages personal growth, society empowers its members to thrive morally and contribute positively.

This concept can be referred to as moral synergy. The combined effect of moral character, moral interaction, and the moral environment is greater than the sum of their individual effects. Understanding these interdependencies helps develop strategies to promote ethical behavior and create a more harmonious, morally upright society (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Moral Framework for HEIs

Conclusion

Integrating structured ethical standards, personal moral values, and essential ethical principles is vital in creating a respectful, inclusive, and high-quality educational environment in higher education institutions (HEIs). These elements collectively support the holistic development of students and faculty, ensuring that ethical considerations are central to academic and personal growth.

Structured ethical standards, outlined in codes of ethics or institutional policies, emphasize core values such as respect, integrity, and responsibility. Universities X, Y, and Z demonstrate this commitment by focusing on aspects like academic freedom, social responsibility, and the integration of religious values. These standards guide behavior and foster a culture of respect and inclusivity within the academic community.

Personal moral standards among faculty and students reveal diverse perspectives on moral values and identity. Themes such as moral goodness, personal attributes, and aspirations highlight how individual experiences shape ethical views. These unstructured moral standards significantly influence how individuals face ethical challenges and shape the moral climate of the institution. Essential ethical standards in higher education include values such as spirituality, dignity, and integrity. Promoting these standards within HEIs is crucial for creating an ethical, inclusive, and supportive educational environment. By fostering these values, institutions can ensure that all academic community members are treated with dignity and respect, thereby enhancing the quality of education.

The findings of this study are beneficial to educational institutions, both for the students and faculty members. However, looking at things from a broader perspective, many ethical standards may still be explored with participants having different faith beliefs and ways of life. The proposed framework presented in this study may be a guide to school administrators across primary, secondary, and tertiary levels in integrating values education or ethics education into the subject courses of the students.

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